

Deliverable Report D6.1

INSIGHT Corporate Identity (project logo, website, brochure, poster)

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Project Full Name	Integrated Models for the Development and Assessment of High Impact Chemicals and Materials
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Instrument	Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Project Start Date	01 January 2024
Duration	48 months

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¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Acronyms listed in this document	
CI	Corporate Identity
EC	European Commission
R&I	Research & Innovation

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Executive Summary

In today's ubiquitous availability of news and expert information, a strong visibility is key for an R&I project, such as INSIGHT, to remain memorable and thus become an easily identifiable, findable and reliable provider of relevant scientific results and innovative advances. Such 'memorability' is best conveyed through the design of a strong corporate identity (CI), which combines the idea behind the project with its acronym and logo and supports both with a striking colour scheme.

The INSIGHT Project had designed its CI already at the proposal stage.

This deliverable report introduces the INSIGHT CI that had been created, and describes its further elaboration through the establishment of a full colour scheme, and the design and development of several templates, online communication channels and websites, and a range of promotional print material. All of these items reproduce the INSIGHT CI and thereby guarantee its wider use and distribution through the individual communication and dissemination activities of each INSIGHT partner.

The INSIGHT CI based following communication and dissemination material has been developed:

- Templates for presentations, deliverable reports and posters,
- An INSIGHT Project public website,
- An INSIGHT Project LinkedIn page, and
- Print media (i.e. 3-fold flyers and a roll-up banner).

The INSIGHT partners are encouraged to reproduce the Project's CI, and to use the templates and promotional materials provided as often as possible.

All communication and dissemination material will be updated regularly, and INSIGHT partners using the material are encouraged to provide feedback about the materials' usability and responses received.

1 INSIGHT Logo, Colour Scheme and Font

The INSIGHT logo and colour scheme were set during the proposal writing phase to match the association with the project acronym 'INSIGHT' (for 'Integrated Models for the Development and Assessment of High Impact Chemicals and Materials' (Project title)); these include:

- Ideation & Innovation (symbolised by a light bulb), and
- Chemistry (symbolised by the molecular structure inside the light bulb).

1.1 The INSIGHT Logo and Colour Scheme

Figure 1 shows the INSIGHT logo in its original colour scheme, which plays on the colours of the European Union, without copying them.

Figure 1: Illustration of the INSIGHT logo and indication of its colour scheme.

The INSIGHT icon, shown in Figure 2, retains the attributes of and associations with the INSIGHT logo (see above). The icon is used as a favicon on the INSIGHT public website (see section 3 below), and in illustrations, where space is limited, and where the full details about the INSIGHT Project are provided elsewhere.

The INSIGHT colour scheme was set around the following prescribed colours: (a) the darkest shade of blue in the original logo (i.e. hex code #13293a), (b) the lightest shade of blue in the original logo (i.e. hex code #196db3), and (c) a medium shade of yellow (i.e. hex code #fdcc11), used in the central icon (i.e. the light bulb) of the INSIGHT logo (see Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 2: Illustration of the INSIGHT icon.

Figure 3: Colour test of the three selected central INSIGHT colours: the existing logo is tested against each one of the colours as a background in both its original colours, black, white, and grey.

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Figure 4: Illustration of the three central colours (and their tints and shades) of the INSIGHT colour scheme that were picked from the existing logo. (source: https://www.w3schools.com/colors/colors_picker.asp)

Figure 5 illustrates, how two additional complementary contrasting colours were selected, in order to broaden the range of available colours for illustrations both on the website, in social media and in print; shades of red will be used to emphasise highlight and alerts in communication media.

Figure 5: Illustration of the selection of colours to broaden the range of available colours for the INSIGHT promotional materials (i.e. website, social media, flyers, posters, banners): (a) two complementary (i.e. triadic) contrasting colours were picked (i.e. a magenta shade (hex code #b3196d), and a green shade (hex code #6db319)) using an online colour picker tool (source: <https://htmlcolorcodes.com/color-picker/>); (b) the tints and shades of the chosen colours are defined in their hex codes (https://www.w3schools.com/colors/colors_picker.asp).

1.2 The INSIGHT Font

The INSIGHT font was chosen to be clean (i.e. sans serif) and easily available (i.e. part of the standard Microsoft Office suite), so that all partners could easily use the templates for presentations and reports devised by the INSIGHT Project, without having to install new fonts, or rendering the templates unrecognisable upon an automatic change, when using them in a system without the font. The selection fell on the Gill Sans typeface, illustrated in Figure 6. This typeface was developed in 1928 to provide a sans-serif typeface that combined the ‘monumental’ Roman capitals in its upper case with ‘old style’ serif letters in its lower case (omitted in its italic variations), whilst yielding a compact font of clear geometric lines. It is a compact font that can easily be compressed and expanded.

The Gills Sans typeface was subsequently used for the development of the entire suite of the INSIGHT Project’s communication and dissemination materials:

- (a) templates for slide presentations (see section 2.1), deliverable reports (see section 2.2), and poster presentations (see section 2.3) by the INSIGHT Project,
- (b) promotional print material (i.e. flyers and roll-up banners) (see section 4, and
- (c) the INSIGHT public website (www.INSIGHT-Project.org) (see section 3 below).

Figure 6 Illustration of the Gill Sans typeface. (source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gill_Sans)

2 Templates for INSIGHT Presentations and Reports

The corporate identity (CI) of the INSIGHT Project represents a strong unique identifier of the project to all stakeholders (including those identified as direct stakeholders of the INSIGHT Project, and the identified target dissemination and communication groups), as well as the wide international research and innovation (R&I) communities concerned with chemicals and materials and their safety and sustainability. In order to use the CI to its full potential, several templates have been developed and provided to the project consortium.

2.1 INSIGHT Presentation Templates

The slide presentation template, illustrated in Figure 7, is made available to the INSIGHT partners in the form of *.PPTX and *.POTX files provided on the Project's shared Google Drive.

Figure 7: Composite figure of two screenshots illustrating the design and content of the INSIGHT slide presentation template, provided to the INSIGHT partners in the form of *.PPTX and *.POTX files.

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2.3 INSIGHT Poster Template

The poster template depicted in Figure 9 predominantly aims to provide suggestions for a possible layout of a poster, using the INSIGHT colour scheme, font and images.

The suggestion is offered in a specific size (i.e. A0 = 841 mm x 1189 mm), and in the file formats *.PPTX and *.POTX. The required dimensions of a poster may, however, vary, depending on the display panels provided by the relevant event. The authors of posters are therefore encouraged to use the INSIGHT poster template as a guidance only.

Figure 9: Composite figure of the INSIGHT poster template, predominantly offering design suggestions and original colours, font and images to the authors.

3 The INSIGHT public Website

The public website of the INSIGHT Project (URL: www.INSIGHT-Project.org (i.e. *.eu was not available)) represents the Project's most important means of visibility, and its main channel for dissemination and communication. It provides a first point of information about the project to a wide audience, ranging from the Project's direct stakeholders, who will be provided with links to the website, in order to make specific dissemination material (e.g. articles, publications, presentations) available to them, to registered participants of INSIGHT events (e.g. webinars, meetings), to the wider interested expert community, who is invite to browse the website for the latest Project results, or to sign up for INSIGHT newsletters.

The INSIGHT public website, illustrated in Figure 11, consists of four main pages: (a) the homepage, (b) 'R&I Approach', (c) 'Consortium', and (d) 'News & Press'; a fifth page will be added later, in order to announce INSIGHT events and provide event information to attendees.

The home page of the website has been set up to also work more intuitively on mobile devices: allows the manoeuvring to the different sections *via* both (i) the selection of the relevant page from the top menu, and (b) by scrolling down on the home page.

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Figure 11: Composite figure showing the layout and current pages of the INSIGHT Public website: (a) the home page, (b) 'R&I Approach' [truncated], (c) 'Consortium' [truncated], and (d) 'News & Press' (incl. footer).

The website will furthermore be the main source and archive of all news articles published by the INSIGHT Project as 'web posts'. A summary of all posts, as well as their title and publication date is provided on the 'News & Press' page; clicking on any one of the 'cards' depicted for each post will open the full web post on a new page, as illustrated in Figure 10.

The Project aims to publish at least one post per month. While this target should not be difficult to achieve once the Project is producing numerous results and attending many conferences to present these, news articles at the beginning of the project will predominantly focus on an introduction to the project itself, as well as its consortium: partner profiles will be published every other week, introducing INSIGHT's partner organisations and their individual staff.

Figure 10: Screenshot of a web post page, containing news articles written and published by the Project.

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4 INSIGHT Print Media

Printed promotional material about the INSIGHT Project has been designed and is made available to the partners, in order to provide visibility and support communication and dissemination activities at in-person events. Every partner is encouraged to use the *.PDF formats provided and to arrange its printing locally and as required; the partners are encouraged to keep the printing of paper 3-fold flyers to a minimum, but the Project recognises that these small illustrations are still powerful vehicles of the Project's visibility and corporate identity.

4.1 The INSIGHT flyer

Figure 12 illustrates the *.PDF file of the 3-fold flyer that has been created for the INSIGHT Project. This first version of the flyer provides an overview of its objectives and planned R&I approach. The flyer will be updated regularly, in order to reflect the latest project results.

4.2 The INSIGHT Roll-Up Banner

Figure 13 shows a small reproduction of the roll-up banner about the INSIGHT Project.³

Figure 12: Reproduction of the 3-fold flyer (A4, version 1) about the INSIGHT Project.

Figure 13: Reproduction of the roll-up banner (84 cm x 206 cm) about the INSIGHT Project.

³ The dimensions have been set to match those of the printing service that will provide the first set of roll-up banners to the coordinator; INSIGHT partners are encouraged to have their own banners printed and check if their local printing service requires different dimensions.

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5 INSIGHT Social Media

The INSIGHT Project decided to use LinkedIn as a social media platform only (i.e. no X (formerly Twitter) account will be created for the INSIGHT Project). This decision was taken based on the increasing critique directed at X, as well as the analytics of the social media traffic of other, comparable projects, such as the MACRAMÉ Project⁴, which commenced in December 2022 and maintains both an X and a LinkedIn account: the analytics show that an increasingly negligible number of referrals to the MACRAMÉ Project website come from X users. The dominating social media platform for news about R&I projects is LinkedIn.

The INSIGHT Project's LinkedIn page is a registered company page (i.e. URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/insight-ssbd>, LinkedIn handle: @INSIGHT-SSbD). Figure 14 shows a screengrab of the page, viewed as a LinkedIn member.

Both the INSIGHT Coordination team and the Communication&Dissemination partners Warrant Hub and AcumenIST are registered authors, who can communicate (i.e. in the form of posts and job adverts) through the Project's LinkedIn page.

The Project aims to provide new posts through this page at least every other week.

Figure 14: Screengrab of the INSIGHT Project's LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/insight-ssbd>, LinkedIn handle: @INSIGHT-SSbD).

6 Conclusion

The INSIGHT Project has developed a strong corporate identity (CI), consisting of a memorable logo, a striking colour scheme and a clear font that is easily reproducible.

The INSIGHT CI is made visible and promoted through a large portfolio of promotional material, including various templates for easy use and reproduction by the Project partners, large- and small-scale printed media, a social media channel, and the Project's main website.

In order to retain the strong recognition potential of the INSIGHT CI, all media and communication channels must be updated regularly. INSIGHT partners are encouraged to use (and report) the CI promotional material provided, and to give feedback about its useability to the Project's Communication&Dissemination partners.

⁴ www.macrame-project.eu (website accessed: 11.04.2024)

